

UNRAVELING THE SYNERGY BETWEEN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT ENGAGEMENT, SUSTAINABLE AWARENESS, AND HOSPITALITY MANAGEMENT SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Student engagement and sustainability awareness shape the development of hospitality management skills among Senior High School learners, emphasizing their growing relevance in preparing future industry professionals. As active participation in learning activities and heightened environmental consciousness continue to influence competence-building, the study explored how these factors collectively enhance students' hospitality management skills which covers communication, customer service, and environmental stewardship. The study involved 181 Senior High School students under the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Track, Home Economics Strand. Guided by a descriptive-correlational design, this research determined a representative sample using the Taro Yamane formula, and employed a modified instrument adapted from Bhutto et al. (2021) to measure the key variables. Descriptive analyses showed that the participants have generally high level of engagement and awareness of sustainable hospitality practices and proficiency in hospitality skills. Regression result reveal that participants with higher levels of engagement demonstrated higher hospitality management skills, underscoring the value of interactive, participatory learning in improving professional readiness. The findings suggest the need for hospitality education programs to integrate sustainability-centered curricula, immersive internship opportunities, and academic industry partnerships to strengthen alignment with workforce expectations and global industry shifts. For broader understanding and validation, the study recommends future research utilizing longitudinal and qualitative designs to monitor students' transition into professional practice and assess contextual differences across educational institutions.

Keywords: *Student engagement, Sustainability awareness, Hospitality management skill*

INTRODUCTION

The hospitality sector is constantly changing, driven mainly by the integration of sustainability practices aimed at reducing environmental impact, operational costs, and building resilience against emerging threats. Modern hospitality professionals are expected to demonstrate not only strong management skills but also sustainability-oriented decision-making aligned with global development goals. Consequently, education providers, especially at the senior high school level, play a critical role in developing future practitioners by embedding engagement, competencies, and sustainability in the curriculum. Early exposure to sustainable practices helps shape students' values and attitudes toward responsible service, forming the foundation for future professional excellence.

Duran and Mariñas (2024) found that sustainability education remains at an early stage of adoption, calling for deeper integration to enhance students' capacity to address real-world challenges. However, most of the available research and sustainability-based hospitality education has targeted tertiary-level education (Choe & Kim, 2020; Zeng et al., 2024; Zizka & Varga, 2020). An important gap exists in empirical evidence of how senior high school students, especially those in the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Home Economics developed hospitality management skills from engagement, and developing sustainability awareness.

Wang and Kim (2020) assert that integrating sustainability concepts into hospitality education fosters environmentally friendly behavior and educates students on global environmental issues, while Duran and Mariñas (2024) identify waste management and energy use reduction as significant sustainability components in hospitality operations, underscoring the increasing importance of sustainability education experiences in hospitality to effectively prepare students for their future practice.

Building on this multidimensional model, Kahu and Nelson (2022) emphasize that engagement results from a dynamic interaction among students, teachers, and institutional contexts, which together influence motivation and learning outcomes. In hospitality education, these dimensions are particularly relevant, as engagement often occurs in experiential and applied settings. Bigné et al. (2023) note that hands-on and laboratory-based training fosters both emotional and cognitive engagement by immersing students in authentic experiences that require reflection and problem-solving. Thus, engagement in hospitality education goes beyond classroom participation; it becomes an active, reflective process that connects theory to practice and enhances students' professional growth.

Communication skills enable students to interact confidently and professionally with guests, colleagues, and supervisors, fostering guest satisfaction and operational

efficiency. Nguyen and Bilgihan (2023) noted that sustainability-oriented hospitality programs enhance communication and interpersonal abilities through collaborative and ethics-based learning environments. Similarly, Wood (2020) emphasized that communication-focused instruction strengthens both technical and interpersonal competencies, improving students' employability and readiness for the service environment.

This study addressed three key gaps: the theoretical gap regarding the limited incorporation of engagement and sustainability in skill formation; the empirical gap due to the lack of data at the senior high school level; and the contextual gap concerning the Philippine TVL–Home Economics setting. The identified gap in research underscores the importance of focusing on this crucial period of development. By understanding how these values and behaviors are initially formed, educators and industry professionals can better guide and support students in becoming well-rounded and responsible hospitality professionals (Zeng et al., 2024; Bagon et al., 2023) confirmed that Existing research in hospitality tends to focus on higher education, leaving the secondary level under-explored. Many studies have limited scope and small sample sizes, failing to capture how early engagement and exposure to sustainability shape students' knowledge and practical skills. This is a significant gap, as senior high school is where future hospitality professionals receive their initial training before entering the industry or pursuing further education in hospitality and tourism management. Addressing this gap will provide essential context for implementing engagement and sustainability initiatives to build practical skills, leading to more responsive, inclusive, and industry-driven education programs.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employed a quantitative correlational research design to systematically measure and analyze the relationships among student engagement, awareness of sustainable hospitality practices, and hospitality management skills. Following the methodological guidance of Creswell and Creswell (2021) this design enabled the collection of measurable data for statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, ensuring objectivity and precision. The descriptive component identified the participants' levels of engagement, sustainability awareness, and management skills, while the correlational component examined how variations in these factors relate to one another. Aligned with the perspectives of Cohen et al. (2018) correlational research is well-suited for educational studies because it explores natural relationships without manipulating variables.

Participants and Sampling Procedure. The study involved 181 Senior High School students under the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Track, Home Economics Strand, from four selected public schools in Bukidnon offering hospitality-related courses. A simple random sampling technique was employed to ensure that each student had an equal chance of being selected, thereby minimizing selection bias and improving representativeness. The sample size of 181 was determined using the Yamane (1967) formula from a total population of 331 students.

Research Instruments. The researcher developed a structured questionnaire based on validated research instruments from recent studies in hospitality and education published between 2019 and 2024. The research instrument, adapted from Dr. Brenda's pre-validation framework, measured three core variables relevant to senior high school hospitality education: Student Engagement, Awareness of Sustainable Hospitality Practices, and Hospitality Management Skills. Student Engagement items were based on the works of Mendez et al. (2021), Li et al. (2023), and Auh et al. (2022), focusing on behavioral, emotional, and cognitive aspects that contribute to positive learning outcomes. Awareness of Sustainable Hospitality Practices was informed by Bhutto et al. (2021), Kim et al. (2021), and Rahman et al. (2023), emphasizing students' understanding of waste management, energy conservation, and responsible resource use. Meanwhile, the Hospitality Management Skills component drew from Nguyen and Bilgihan (2023), Carlisle et al. (2023), and Zeng et al. (2024), highlighting essential competencies in communication, customer service, and environmental management required for sustainable hospitality operations.

Validity and Reliability of the Research Instruments. Prior to data collection, the research instrument underwent a rigorous validation and reliability process to ensure accuracy and appropriateness. Content validity was confirmed through expert evaluation by hospitality education specialists, while a pilot test with 30 non-participants allowed for statistical reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha. Results demonstrated satisfactory to excellent internal consistency across all constructs, including Behavioral Engagement ($\alpha = 0.654$), Emotional Engagement ($\alpha = 0.749$), Cognitive Engagement ($\alpha = 0.757$), Waste Management ($\alpha = 0.806$), Energy Conservation ($\alpha = 0.785$), Communication Skills ($\alpha = 0.979$), Customer Service Skills ($\alpha = 0.762$), and Environmental Skills ($\alpha = 0.746$), all meeting or exceeding the acceptable reliability threshold of 0.70.

Scoring Procedure. The study utilized a five-point Likert scale to measure the participants' level of understanding, engagement, and awareness related to sustainable hospitality practices. This scale allowed participants to indicate the extent of their agreement or frequency of behavior, ranging from one (lowest) to five (highest). The following scoring system was applied to interpret the data collected from the questionnaire responses.

Data Gathering Procedure and Ethical Considerations. The researcher secured ethical clearance from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee (LC REC), ensuring that all procedures aligned with established ethical standards for studies involving human participants. A structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to gather data on student engagement, sustainability awareness, and hospitality management skills. Participants were identified in coordination with school administrators, and data collection was conducted within school premises to ensure proper oversight. With formal permission from school authorities, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires to Senior High School students enrolled in the TVL–Home Economics strand in selected public secondary schools in Bukidnon. Each participant voluntarily answered the survey within 20–30 minutes, after which the completed questionnaires were retrieved, organized, encoded, and subjected to appropriate statistical analyses.

based on the study's objectives.

The study strictly adhered to the Belmont Principles Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice. Respect for Persons was upheld by ensuring voluntary participation, allowing respondents to withdraw anytime, securing informed consent, and protecting anonymity. Beneficence was demonstrated by minimizing risks, ensuring participant comfort, and guaranteeing that the study would benefit the academic community by improving teaching and learning practices in hospitality education. Justice was observed by ensuring fair participant selection and equal opportunity for inclusion, avoiding undue burden or exclusion of any group. All collected data were handled with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes, maintaining both participant trust and the integrity of the research process.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1. Summary Table of Engagement

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Behavioral	4.06	High	0.56
Emotional	4.18	High	0.60
Cognitive	4.06	High	0.59
Engagement	4.10	High	0.40

Table 1 presents the summary of Engagement, among these dimensions, emotional engagement stood out with the highest mean of 4.18 (High), while both behavioral and cognitive engagement followed closely behind, each with a mean of 4.06 (High). These results suggest that students are not only active and intellectually engaged in their learning but also emotionally invested and motivated throughout their classroom experiences. The consistently high scores across all dimensions highlight a positive and vibrant learning environment that fosters comprehensive student engagement.

Overall, high levels of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement suggest that students are deeply involved mentally and emotionally in their learning experiences. Recent research supports this view, demonstrating that multi-dimensional engagement is strongly associated with academic performance and personal growth (Abun et al., 2024). Castrodes et al. (2025) confirmed their study that students who excel in their overall management course are those who have initiative and are motivated. Furthermore, teacher support is equally important; when instructors create a positive and caring environment, students are more motivated, actively participate, and make more significant investments in their studies (Jia & Cheng, 2024).

From the researcher's perspective, these results affirm that a student-centered and interactive learning environment one that integrates hands-on practice, collaboration, and reflection effectively promotes comprehensive engagement. The hospitality program necessitates full student engagement because it develops their professional skills and

emotional resilience, enabling them to succeed in fast-changing work environments.

Table 2. Summary Table of Awareness of Sustainable Hospitality Practices

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Waste management and; Energy conservation practices	4.38 4.23	High High	0.58 0.57
Awareness of sustainable hospitality practices	4.30	High	0.43

Table 2 presents the summary table of the participants' understanding of sustainable hospitality practices based on waste management and energy conservation practices. The results show that both dimensions reached *High* interpretation levels through a composite mean of 4.30 and a standard deviation of 0.43 which shows participants maintain strong comprehension of sustainability principles for hospitality education and operations.

Waste management practices were the leading dimension, with the mean of 4.38, categorized as High, while energy conservation practices followed closely at 4.23, also High. The data further indicate that students understand the practices in waste management, like segregation and recycling, more than they understand methods for the conservation of energy. It is plausible to consider that this trend may emanate from the fact that waste management practices are more tangible and observable, enabling students to participate actively and internalize such behavior during laboratory exercises and practical activities.

Recent research corroborates this observation. Rani et al. (2024) identified that with increased environmental knowledge, hospitality students show a significant improvement in engaging in sustainable behaviors, especially in waste reduction and recycling. Similarly, the study on hotel operations in Malaysia reveals that the practices related to waste management are more widely applied and better recognized compared to the more abstract sustainability measures, such as energy efficiency, because of their practical applicability and immediate visibility (Rassiah et al., 2024; Muqtader et al., 2023). These findings indicate that the integration of concrete sustainability practices into hospitality education effectively enhances the students' awareness, promotes responsible environmental behavior, and prepares them for professional roles related to sustainable hospitality operations.

From the researcher's point of view, the overall High ranking across both dimensions confirms the hypothesis that, in this learning environment, awareness of sustainability is appropriately internalized. Students have a good understanding of managing waste and conserving energy; therefore, they consider environmental care a part of their professional preparedness. This certainly affirms that continuous exposure to academic and laboratory settings promotes not just awareness but also a sense of accountability toward environmental stewardship.

Table 3. Summary Table of Hospitality Skills

Dimensions	Mean	Description	Interpretation	SD
Communication Skills	4.08	Agree	High	0.57
Customer Service Skills	4.05	Agree	High	0.64
Environmental Skills	4.12	Agree	High	0.58
Hospitality Skills	3.06	Slightly Agree	Moderate	0.29

Table 3 presents the summary of participants' assessments of their hospitality skills across three major dimensions: communication skills, customer service skills, and environmental skills. From this, it is seen that participants rated all the three dimensions as *High*, since the mean turned out to be 4.08, 4.05, and 4.12, respectively. However, the overall composite mean for hospitality skills is 3.06, interpreted as *Moderate*, with a standard deviation of 0.29.

This finding suggests that, in individual skill areas, students generally demonstrate proficiency, particularly in environmental awareness. However, a balanced mastery of all hospitality competencies as an integrated professional skill set might still be developing. The high ratings in communication and customer service highlighted their interpersonal readiness, while the overall rating was moderate, implying a need for further practical application and industry exposure.

Among the dimensions, environmental skills ranked highest, with a mean of 4.12 High, to show that the participants felt most confident about competencies related to sustainability, such as reducing waste, conserving resources, and advocating for environmental stewardship. Such environmental competence is supported by recent evidence showing that hospitality students who possess more environmental knowledge are significantly more likely to engage in sustainability practices, especially in reducing waste and managing food waste effectively Rani et al. (2024).

Moreover, research on the students of generation Z in hospitality and tourism exhibits a greater pro environmental awareness that suggests that the students are more open to values and behaviors about sustainability in contemporary settings Loverio et al. (2022). In addition, research on the practical implementations of sustainability education-such as digital learning tools and practical waste management initiatives-are showing how students tend to apply more often and internalize concrete eco-behavioral practices rather than abstractly defined measures such as general energy conservation Muqtader et al. (2023); Student's perceptions of sharing platforms and digital learning. Such findings support the view that tangible sustainability practices in the hospitality curriculum positively foster awareness and actionable competencies so that the environmental skills, particularly those relating to waste management and resource conservation, also become more salient and confidently applied by the students.

From a researcher's perspective, the findings suggest that while students have developed solid foundations in key hospitality competencies, there is still a great need for them to be exposed to applying these competencies holistically in an applied setting. Kim et al.

(2021) imply that such linking of classroom learning to authentic work experiences increases overall hospitality competence, confidence, and adaptability.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of Student Engagement and Awareness of Sustainable Hospitality Practices on Hospitality Management Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.539	.265		5.806	.000
Engagement	.164	.052	.223	3.187**	.002
Sustainable hospitality practices	.197	.048	.290	4.141*	.000

Model Summary

R = 0.399 R² = 0.159 Adj. R² = 0.150 F= 16.873** p = .000

**significant at 0.01 level

*Significant at 0.05 level

Table 4 present the Regression Analysis of Student Engagement and Awareness of Sustainable Hospitality Practices on Hospitality Management Skills. It shows that student engagement and the awareness of sustainable hospitality practice significantly predict the development of hospitality management skills, (F= 16.873, p-.000) to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Findings further revealed that the two variables jointly account for 15.9% of the variation in the development of hospitality management skills. The remaining 84.1% may be attributed to other factors such as practicum exposure, teacher guidance, and institutional support in developing students' competence in hospitality settings.

These findings suggest that when students are more engaged and more aware of sustainable practices, their competency in hospitality skills improves. In practical terms, engagement can be fostered through flipped-classroom methods in hospitality education, where students actively discuss and simulate real hospitality tasks in a two-way, online, or in-person setting (Wang and Chen 2022).

From these results, it can be established that the theoretical frameworks of the study are well represented. The engagement of students manifests Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory through active participation, reflection, and application of hospitality tasks, while awareness of sustainable hospitality practices embodies the principles of Sustainable Development Theory through the promotion of responsible and environmentally conscious decision-making. Together, these two variables greatly contribute to the development of hospitality management skills. These findings suggest the importance of experiential learning and integration of sustainability in preparing senior high school students for professional success within the hospitality industry.

Conclusions

The study confirmed the empirical link between student engagement and awareness of hospitality sustainability practices in developing hospitality management skills among Senior High School TVL–Home Economics students. Anchored on Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory (1984), the findings affirmed that practical activities, simulations, and immersions enhance students’ motivation and ability to transform learning experiences into professional competence, showing that hospitality learning is most effective when students engage in authentic or simulated practice environments.

However, while the model explained a significant portion of skill development, it also revealed that external factors such as institutional support, industry exposure, and quality of work immersion likely influence competence formation. These limitations point to future research directions focusing on longitudinal tracking and qualitative exploration to better capture these dynamics.

Recommendations

1. Hospitality educators may enhance student engagement by using active learning strategies such as simulations, role-playing, and real-world applications, while also integrating teamwork, problem-solving, and critical thinking through group work and industry exposure. They should likewise provide consistent feedback and recognition to sustain motivation and strengthen students’ emotional engagement in both classroom and laboratory activities.
2. Deans and administrators may enhance sustainability education by integrating topics like waste management and energy conservation into the curriculum, promoting school-based projects, and establishing partnerships with tourism and environmental organizations for authentic field exposure. They should also provide skills development programs and internship opportunities to strengthen students’ communication, customer service, and operational competencies in real hospitality settings.
3. Local Government Units (LGUs) and the Department of Tourism (DOT) may intensify their collaboration with schools in promoting educational and training programs that advance both skill development and environmental stewardship.
4. Future researchers may use qualitative or mixed-method designs and consider longitudinal approaches to gain deeper insights into students’ sustainability and engagement experiences while examining their long-term impact on career readiness and employability in the hospitality industry.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to ethical guidelines in conducting research with human participants. Before starting the data collection process, the researcher ensured that informed consent was obtained from all participants. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, how the data would be used, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Additionally, the confidentiality of the participants’ information was guaranteed, and any

identifying information was removed during the data analysis process to protect their privacy.

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